

This document provides you with an **overview of all the questions and answering possibilities** of the self-assessment tool of ENoLL.

We strongly advise you to **go through all the questions** in this document to make sure you understand the questions in the self-assessment tool **in advance** and **to make sure you collect all the needed information before starting to complete the tool online**.

The tool is based on the harmonized evaluation framework developed by ENoLL and covers **6 chapters and 15 criteria of sustainable Living Labs**.

The tool allows you to self-assess the sustainability and maturity of your Living Lab.

If you have questions around this document, you can always reach us via enollnetwork@enoll.org.

By completing the self-assessment tool, you agree to your details being held electronically by the European Network of Living Labs.

ENoLL will process your personal data on the legal basis of Art. 6, case b) of GDPR.

Your data will be processed in compliance with regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the council of 27 April 2016, on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (GDPR) and Law 2018/40581 of 30 July 2018 on protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data.

Agreeing to this statement allow ENoLL to contact you in relation to this self-assessment if necessary.

You can exercise the right of access, rectification, erasure, restriction of processing, portability, and objection, by sending an e-mail to privacy@enoll.org.

This page provides you with useful information about the Living Lab concept, levels, and evaluation framework. Reading it will help you to answer upcoming questions better.

A Living Lab is made up of 3 levels, as described by [Schoorman](#) in 2015.

- On the **macro level**, a Living Lab is a public-private-people partnership consisting of different stakeholders, organized to carry out Living Lab research and Living Lab projects. We refer to this level as **the Living Lab constellation**.
- On the **meso level**, we discern the Living Lab innovation projects that are being carried out within the Living Lab constellation. We refer to this as **Living Lab project(s)**.
- The **(research) activities** that are deployed in a Living Lab we label as **micro level** activities in Living Labs. This consists of **a specific Living Lab methodology** to cultivate user-led insights and surface tacit, experiential, and domain-based knowledge such that it can be further codified and communicated.

Some Living Labs exist where the Living Lab constellation is set up for only one innovation project, which merges the macro and meso level, but we regard these ‘Living Lab as a project’ initiatives as problematic in terms of sustainability and sub-optimal in terms of added value being generated for the actors involved.

This self-assessment focuses on 6 main building blocks and 15 criteria of sustainable Living Labs across these 3 levels of a Living Lab.

More information about this harmonized evaluation framework can be found [here](#).

Below, you may find a graphical overview of these blocks and criteria coming next. Every main block will start with a short description to increase your understanding.

General information organization

First, we'd like to ask some general questions about your organization and yourself.

What is your full name?*

What is your email address? * *We will use this email address to send you the results.*

What is the name of your organization? *

In which country is your organization located? *

To which sector of the quadruple helix is your organization affiliated? *

Select one option

Public administration (e.g., city authorities, ministries, ...)

Private sector (e.g., company, start-up, SME...)

Academia (e.g., universities, research centers...)

Society (e.g., NGOs, community centers...)

Other, namely:

Does your organization host a Living Lab? *

Yes/No

If no go to the next page

What is the name of your Living Lab? *

In which year was your Living Lab founded? *

In which sectors is your Living Lab active? *

Multiple answers are possible.

Agriculture and Agri-food

Circular economy

Culture, creativity, and media

Education and/or vocational training

Emerging technologies (e.g. AI, AI/VR...)

Energy

Environment and climate change

Health and Well Being

Industries and Manufacturing

Mobility

Policies

Regulatory learning

Rural

Smart cities and regions

SME and start-ups

Social innovation and inclusion

Urban

Water (blue economy)

Zero pollution and decarbonization

I don't know

Other, namely

Strategy

This first chapter addresses long-term aspects of a Living Lab, such as *multi-stakeholder participation*, the *orchestration* role of the Living Lab, *collaboration* strategies, and the *business model*. Three criteria are used to assess this part

Governance, including

- *a well-defined and shared vision and mission for the Living Lab, based on real identified needs of quadruple helix actors,*
- *involvement of actors of the quadruple helix on a strategic level*
- *clearly defined roles and responsibilities within the Living Lab governance team*
- *a clear strategy roadmap, including the expected impacts of the Living Lab strategy and the Living Lab projects*

Business Model including

- *a view on the business plan of the Living Lab*
- *a well-defined and described service portfolio for various phases of innovation and collaboration processes*

Ecosystem and collaboration including

- *proof of connections/interest to connect with external (regional/national/ international) innovation ecosystems,*
- *smart and adaptive cooperation/collaboration within the Living Lab design to build trust,*
- *quality of the internal communication processes,*
- *channels and tools within the Living Lab to build trust*

Which different types of stakeholder groups of the quadruple helix are present in the ecosystem of your Living Lab? *

Multiple choice

Public sector

- Local government (e.g., city authorities)
- Regional government (e.g., provinces/states)
- National government (e.g., ministries)
- International government (e.g., EU/UN)
- Funding agencies (national/international)
- Funded organizations (e.g., port authorities)

Private sector

- Industry and large private companies
- Start-ups and SME's
- Angel investors/Accelerator program owners
- Sector organizations and associations

Academia

- Universities
- Schools
- Research centers
- Students
- Science communication centers

Society

- NGO's
- Think Tanks
- Community centers
- Communities of citizens/users
- Open innovation labs/arrangements (e.g., fablab, citizen science...)

Other, namely:

To what degree are the strategic parts shown here below implemented/planned for in the strategic roadmap of your Living Lab? *

Single choice

Something is **in place** when it is fully implemented/operational within your Soil Health Living Lab.

Something is **planned for** if it is still under development. This includes partly implemented processes not covering all aspects in the description (e.g. for SMART goals and objectives: envisioned projects are in place, but expected impacts are missing).

Something is **currently missing** if it is not implemented/operational within your Soil Health Living Lab at this moment.

	In place	Planned for	Currently missing
SMART goals and objectives (description of long-term strategies, envisioned projects, expected impacts)			
Partner contributions (description of how each of the partners involved in the governance of the LL is contributing, e.g. financial, personnel, representation, in-kind)			
Partner responsibilities (description of the role of each of the partners involved in the governance of the LL, i.e. which of the partners is responsible for what, e.g. operations, infrastructure, monitoring...)			
Strategic decision-making processes (rules on the governance level about the ways and frequency of decision taking, i.e. how will decisions be made by the governance of the LL)			

Which types of stakeholder groups are actively involved in: *

- **the development of the shared vision and mission of the Living Lab?**
Stakeholders are actively involved in the mission/vision if they actively participated in the creation of it (e.g., co-creation workshops, community of practice meeting...)
- **the development of a strategic roadmap?**
Stakeholders are actively involved in the mission/vision if they actively participated in the creation of it (e.g., co-creation workshops, community of practice meeting...)
- **the governance structure of the Living Lab?**
Stakeholders are actively involved in the governance structure if they are actively participating in the strategic decision-making processes (e.g., management meetings, advisory board...)

Multiple choice

	Not involved	Involved in the vision/mission	Involved in the development of the strategic roadmap	Involved in the governance structure	A partner agreement is signed with them
Carried forward selected groups of stakeholders from stakeholders question					

How frequently does the managing group/governance team of the Living Lab organizes meetings to monitor the progress of the Living Lab and make strategic decisions? *

Single choice

<1x/year
1x/year
2x/year

3x/year
4x/year
6x/year

monthly
more than monthly

How frequently does the Living Lab internally share strategic decisions, information about upcoming actions, and results of past projects/activities, beyond the scope of an individual Living Lab project, with their strategic partners and Living Lab staff? *

Single choice

We are looking for the frequency of sharing beyond the information shared in the meetings of the managing group and/or governance team.

- | | | |
|----------|---------|-------------------|
| <1X/year | 3x/year | monthly |
| 1x/year | 4x/year | more than monthly |
| 2x/year | 6x/year | |

A business model of a Living Lab describes the way and the key activities via which the Living Lab offers solutions and services to solve problems of their stakeholders, customers and users. Next to this, it describes who are the main stakeholder target groups, customers and users of the Living Lab.

Finally, it determines the necessary resources to do so and describes the costs and revenues of the Living Lab.

Which of the following elements are currently present in the business model of your Living Lab? *

Multiple answers are possible.

Problems & solutions (solutions and services offered by the LL to solve clearly defined problems of stakeholders, users & customers)

Activities & resources (overview of activities performed by the LL, e.g., co-creation workshops, events, survey... supported by the necessary items needed to run the LL, e.g., co-creation space, software, etc.)

Stakeholders, users & customer segments (overview of possible clients paying for the services/solutions of the LL and overview of groups of people needed to be involved in the LL activities)

Costs & revenues (which expenses need to be calculated for to run the LL like personnel, office space... versus how the LL will earn money, e.g., paid services like workshop facilitation, rental of infrastructure, etc.)

Metrics & impacts (how the LL will monitor their clearly defined expected impacts)

None of the above

Living Labs use so-called Living Lab innovation cycles to run their Living Lab projects. Two of the most common used methodologies in Living Labs are the innovation lifecycle approach and the Living Lab integrative process.

Within the innovation lifecycle approach four phases are identified: exploration, co-creation, experimentation, and evaluation.

[The Living Lab integrative process](#) uses 3 spaces (problem-solution-deployment), divided in 8 steps like shown in the picture here below

Living Lab services are mostly related to one or more of these identified innovation phases and/or steps.

Some common services are:

- testing and validation services (e.g., end-user engagement, rapid prototyping, experimentation, usability, real-life testing...)
- innovation network orchestration (e.g., community and network building, stakeholder mapping, stakeholder events...)
- Living Lab project planning and management (Living Lab as a service)
- co-creation services (e.g., idea selection, facilitation workshops, focus groups, co-design...)
- capacity building services (e.g., trainings, mentoring, awareness raising...)
- advisory services (e.g., analytical/research services, benchmarking, foresight, regulation support...)
- market and sales support (e.g., deployment services, scaling up solutions to other Living Labs...)
- infrastructure and data management services (e.g., equipment and facility rental, Living Lab as research/technology infrastructure)

For which of the different steps of the Living Lab innovation cycle is your Living Lab offering Living Lab services to its customers? *

In this self-assessment, we use the Living Lab integrative process to match the Living Lab services since this process is the most detailed approach.

Multiple answers are possible.

Practice selection (e.g., idea selection, visioning/missioning exercises)

Integration of stakeholders (e.g., community and network building, stakeholder mapping, coordination & moderation of stakeholders)

Identification of barriers (e.g., analytical/research services, focus groups)

Co-creation/co-design of solutions

Piloting a solution (e.g., rapid prototyping, experimentation, usability, real-life testing)

Evaluating a solution (e.g., end-user engagement, analytical/research services)

Demonstrating a solution (e.g., equipment and facility rental, Living Lab as research/technology infrastructure)

Exploiting a solution (e.g., deployment services, scaling up to other Living Labs)

Other, namely:

None of the above

Good relationships between the Living Lab and its internal partners and external customers, suppliers, and other stakeholders (networks) are crucial for the viability of a Living Lab.

Internal business management processes are describing the ways the Living Lab interacts and communicates with its internal partners and Living Lab team staff (e.g., minutes of governance meetings, frequency of team meetings...)

External business management processes are describing the way the Living Lab interacts with (possible) clients and (possible) new partners of the Living Lab. This is not the same as the community management processes with the users of the Living Lab (e.g., offering procedures of the Living Lab to the client, intake processes of new partners...)

Ethics management processes are describing the way the Living Lab ensures working in an ethical way.

Intellectual property (IP) management processes are describing the way the Living Lab deals with the ownership of results of Living Lab projects/products/services/solutions/...

Which types of management processes are in place in your Living Lab? *

Something is **in place** when it is fully implemented/operational within your organization/Living Lab

Something is **planned for** if it is still under development (this includes partly implemented processes)

Something is **currently missing** if it is not implemented/operational within your organization/Living Lab at this moment

Multiple answers are possible.

	In place	Planned for	Currently missing
Internal business management and processes (<i>existing partners and Living Lab team staff</i>)			
External business management and processes (<i>clients and new possible partners of the Living Lab</i>)			
Ethics management			
Intellectual property (IP) management			

With how many individual Living Labs or other innovation networks has your Living Lab been actively collaborating over the last 3 years on a local, regional, national, or international scale beyond the scope of one individual Living Lab project? *

Local collaboration is collaboration within a city/municipality

Regional collaboration is collaboration within a province/region/state (e.g. Flanders, Catalunya, Normandy)

National collaboration is collaboration within one country

International collaboration is collaboration beyond borders of one country

	0	1	2	3	4	5	+5	+10
Locally								
Regionally								
Nationally								
Internationally								

Operations

The second chapter of this self-assessment is looking at the way the Living Lab manages its operations, including human resources and necessary equipment & infrastructure of the Living Lab. Three evaluation criteria are used to assess this part:

Human resources: including

- availability of qualified staff
- assignment of qualified staff to different roles and responsibilities

Operations: including

- running and coordination of Living Lab projects
- monitoring processes for operational aspects of the Living Lab

Equipment and infrastructure: including

- allocation of necessary Living Lab equipment and infrastructures (e.g., software, hardware, spaces) to the Living Lab team
- availability of necessary Living Lab equipment and infrastructures (e.g., software, hardware, spaces) to the Living Lab team, indicated in time (from continuous to rarely)

When running or setting up a Living Lab at the operational level it is important to define and assign different roles within the Living Lab. The most common roles in an operational Living Lab team are:

- **Living Lab manager**, focusing on the macro-level of the Living Lab by initiating and monitoring the Living Lab strategy via the development of Living Lab projects for their utilizers, while managing the day-by-day activities of the Living Lab.
- **Project manager(s)**, managing entire individual Living Lab projects with a defined scope (meso-level).
- **Panel manager(s)**, planning and coordinating the interaction with a panel of users, citizens and other actors involved in Living Lab activities, by identifying and recruiting these users, while interacting with them and safeguarding the user-centricity of the Living Lab methodologies and activities.
- **Pilot manager(s)**, facilitating the implementation and testing of innovative solutions within the real-life contexts of the users of a Living Lab project.
- **Researcher(s)**, also called Human Interaction specialist(s), designing, and planning the innovation process in an integrative way, while analysing the results of user-centred interaction activities.
- **Communication responsible**, in charge of communicating with a panel of users (citizens and other stakeholders)

How frequently are the following equipment and infrastructure of your Living Lab available to the Living Lab team to be used? *

The purpose of this question is to understand how flexible the operational Living Lab team can use the necessary equipment and infrastructures to run Living Lab activities and projects. Logically, it will be much more difficult to run Living Lab projects and/or activities if for network spaces like co-creation rooms or testing facilities like fab lab spaces are only very irregularly available to be used by the team.

	Not available	Irregularly (<50%)	Regularly (50-90%)	Continuously (>90%)
Office spaces				
Testing facilities (e.g., fab lab space, demonstration space...)				
Prototype building laboratories (i.e. 3D Printing, Electronics, Tools workbenches etc)				
Network spaces (e.g., spaces for co-creation, events...)				
Co-creation materials (e.g., flipcharts/office supplies, LEGO...)				
Communication and interaction platform/tools (e.g., Mailchimp, Teams, Slack...)				
Co-creation platforms/tools (e.g., Miro, Mentimeter...)				
Co-creation/experimentation devices (e.g., smartphones, iPads, computers, wearables...)				
Other equipment or infrastructure				

What other type of equipment or infrastructure is available within your Living Lab?

Only if other in previous question ≠ not available

NON mandatory open ended.

Openness

This third chapter investigates the openness of the Living Lab by focusing on the *processes, partnerships, feedback, and IP protection*. Two evaluation criteria are used to assess this part:

Innovation partnerships, projects, and processes, including

- reflective and iterative approach of the Living Lab
- ethical approach of the Living Lab
- openness towards new partners and investors
- presence of the necessary transparent data agreements between the Living Lab and its partners, stakeholders, and users
- level of transparency of the Living Lab

Ownership of results, including

- feedback protection
- shared vs. formal ownership
- intellectual property (IP) processes

An **iterative approach** is an approach in which the content of discussions and the outcomes of activities and even the next steps are adapted over the course of the innovation cycle. Learning from earlier Living Lab activities is used to influence the inputs for subsequent activities.

A good example of this iterative approach, next to the Living Lab integrative process we explained earlier, is for instance the Double Diamond Framework (<https://www.designcouncil.org.uk/our-resources/framework-for-innovation/>).

An **ethical approach** in innovation involves integrating moral principles and values into the development and implementation of new ideas, products, and technologies. It emphasizes the importance of considering the broader impact on society, the environment, and future generations.

This approach advocates for transparency, inclusivity, and fairness, ensuring that innovations do not disproportionately benefit or harm specific groups. It also promotes accountability, encouraging innovators to take responsibility for the potential consequences of their creations. By prioritizing ethics, innovators can build trust, enhance social well-being, and contribute to sustainable and equitable progress.

How is your Living Lab safeguarding a reflective, iterative and ethical approach to (transdisciplinary) collaboration? *

Multiple answers are possible.

- The Living Lab is using Living Lab iterative processes (co-creation, exploration, experimentation, evaluation) throughout the execution of Living Lab projects
- Innovations are iterated based on feedback from stakeholders in the previous step(s) of the innovation cycle.
- The tools and methods used by the Living Lab stimulate feedback capturing and allow customers to develop their innovations in an iterative way.
- Lessons learned are captured throughout the execution of Living Lab projects in a reflective way
- The research of the Living Lab is open to what is happening in the real-life context and to adjust their processes accordingly.
- Reflexive monitoring is one of the key principles of the Living Lab
- The Living Lab has the capability to adjust its roles and processes in response to changing circumstances.
- The Living Lab uses ethical assessments before they participate in projects
- The Living Lab has a code of conduct which defines participation, information sharing, inclusiveness and data privacy and follows ethical principles of experimental and participatory research.
- The Living Lab has appointed a data protection officer
- The Living Lab has made available to the public a privacy policy
- The Living Lab has an ethics committee that oversees and approves the activities and methodologies of its projects.
- The Living Lab always uses a data management plan in its projects
- The Living Lab has dedicated informed consent procedures in its projects
- The Living Lab ethical uses transparency, equality and inclusion in the selection of Living Lab stakeholders (e.g., vulnerable groups of users)
- Other, namely:
- None of the above

The **use, sharing, and licensing of data** within Living Labs is fundamental to their success. Data collected from users and interactions within the Living Lab are used to inform and refine innovations, ensuring they meet real-world needs and expectations. Sharing data among stakeholders — such as researchers, developers, and users — facilitates collaborative development and enhances transparency.

To manage this data effectively, clear licensing agreements are essential. These agreements define how data can be accessed, used, and shared, ensuring that intellectual property rights are respected while fostering an open and collaborative innovation ecosystem.

Proper licensing promotes trust among participants, protects sensitive information, and enables the sustainable and ethical use of data, driving forward meaningful and user-centred innovation.

Intellectual property (IP) in Living Lab innovation presents a dynamic interplay between protecting proprietary knowledge and fostering collaborative development.

Living Lab innovation leverages external ideas and technologies to drive progress, often requiring

a more flexible approach to IP. In this model, companies share and exchange their IP with external partners, such as startups, research institutions, and even competitors, to accelerate innovation and mutual benefit.

Balancing IP protection with openness is crucial; organizations must ensure their core assets are safeguarded while creating frameworks that facilitate sharing and collaboration.

Effective IP management in Living Lab innovation can lead to enhanced creativity, reduced R&D costs, and faster market entry, fostering a more innovative and interconnected ecosystem.

How is your Living Lab implementing the required processes regarding the use, sharing and licensing of data and IP of collaborative outcomes? *

Multiple answers are possible.

- The Living Lab has collaborative agreements in place laying down IP rules, addressing aspects such as ownership, protection, and exploitation of project results prior to the initiation of a project.
- The Living Lab signs confidentiality agreements to protect sensitive information regarding IP or personal data
- The Living Lab ensures a fair distribution of benefits and burden
- The Living Lab signs user agreements that include the privacy policy and non-disclosure clauses (when applicable) with every individual user of its Living Lab projects
- The Living Lab provides details of the technical and organizational measures to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the participants
- The Living Lab provides details of the technical and organizational measures to safeguard the personal data of the participants
- The Living Lab supports the creation of open source and/or common licenses
- The Living Lab applies the first nations principles of OCAP®, establishing how first nation's data and information will be collected, used, or shared. OCAP stands for ownership, control, access, and possession.
- Other, namely:
- None of the above

Which of the following are integrated into the user agreements your Living Lab is signing with every individual user of its projects? *Multiple answers are possible.

- Project information (purpose, timeline, expectations...)
- Inclusion and exclusion criteria
- Voluntary nature of participation
- Privacy protection (including data)
- Feedback protection of participant's (explanations about what will be done/not done with the feedback)
- Intellectual property agreements
- User rights and duties
- Risk assessments of technologies used
- Liabilities protection (e.g., insurances)
- Other, namely:
- None of the above

Users and reality

This fourth chapter considers the ways in which *collaboration with users takes place* and the levels of engagement and participation, by focusing on the implementation of an *iterative Living Lab process in real life contexts* and investigating the quality of used *tools and methods*. Three evaluation criteria are used to assess this part:

User-centricity of the user and stakeholder engagement approach, including

- description and intensity of the user participation
- user impact on the innovation process
- amount of actively involved users in the Living Lab activities

Quality of the iterative Living Lab processes in real-life contexts, including

- adoption of an iterative Living Lab methodology in the user engagement approach
- involvement of users in real life contexts (e.g., at home, work, in the public space)

Appropriateness of the participatory tools and methods, including

- engagement strategies to match evolving needs of users
- range of used tools and methods
- quality and innovativeness of tools and methods to involve users in the different steps of the iterative Living Lab process

Which different types of stakeholders from your ecosystem are participating as users in Living Lab projects and/or activities over the last 3 years? * *If your Living Lab is younger than 3 years, please count all finished Living Lab projects since the foundation of your Living Lab.*

Multiple choice*

Public sector

- Local government (e.g., city authorities)
- Regional government (e.g., provinces/states)
- National government (e.g., ministries)
- International government (e.g., EU/UN)
- Funding agencies (national/international)
- Funded organizations (e.g., port authorities)

Private sector

- Industry and large private companies
- Start-ups and SME's
- Angel investors/Accelerator program owners
- Sector organizations and associations

Academia

- Universities
- Schools
- Research centers
- Students
- Science communication centers

Society

- NGO's
- Think Tanks
- Community centers
- Communities of citizens/users
- Open innovation labs/arrangements (e.g., fablab, citizen science...)

The international association for public participation (IAP2) has developed the spectrum of public participation to define the role of users/participants in participation processes. This spectrum has become an international standard and describes five general modes of participation.

1. **Inform:** to provide users/participants with balanced and objective information to assist them in understanding the problem, alternatives and/or solutions
2. **Consult:** to obtain users/participants feedback or analysis, alternatives and/or decision
3. **Involve:** to work directly with users/participants throughout the process to ensure that their concerns and aspirations are consistently understood and considered
4. **Collaborate:** to partner with users/participants in each aspect of the decision including the development of alternatives and the identification of the preferred solution
5. **Empower:** to place final decision-making in the hands of user/participants

In general, within your Living Lab, to what extent can users/participants in your Living Lab projects exert influence on the different phases of the Living Lab innovation cycle? *

	Not involved	Inform	Consult	Involve	Collaborate	Empower
Problem identification						
Stakeholder integration						
Solution design						
Solution development						
Testing solutions						
Evaluating solutions						
Demonstrating solutions						
Implementing solutions						

How regularly does your organization/Living Lab involve users/participants in their real-life context? *

Real-life contexts are contexts where users/participants spend most of their time physically/virtually in relation to the innovation project (e.g., the real-life context of employees of a company are the offices of the company where they work on a daily base; the real-life context of students is the classroom they spend most of their time in)

	Not at all	Occasionally (<25% of all activities)	Irregularly (25-49% of all project activities/steps)	Regularly (50-75% of all project activities/steps)	Almost always (>75% of all project activities/steps)
Problem identification					
Stakeholder integration					
Solution design					
Solution development					
Testing solutions					
Evaluating solutions					
Demonstrating solutions					
Implementing solutions					

Participatory methods - as described by participatorymethods.org from the Institute of Development Studies - include a range of activities with a common thread: enabling people to play an active and influential part in decisions which affect their lives. This means that people are not just listened to, but also heard, and that their voices shape outcomes. Whether people are involved in analysis, collective decision-making, planning, reflection or evaluation, participatory tools can be used at all phases of Living Lab innovation cycles. Moreover, they are also useful in political processes as tools for strengthening citizen engagement, claiming rights, and holding the powerful to account.

Some key **principles of participatory learning** are:

- the right to participate
- hearing unheard voices
- seeking local knowledge and diversity
- handing over the stick (or pen, or chalk)
- attitude and behaviour change

Finally, participatory tools and methods **support the capacity building of involved stakeholders** beyond the scope of the specific participatory activity.

In which phases of a Living Lab innovation cycle is your Living Lab using participatory tools and methods? *

Multiple choice

This question is asking for different phases of the Living Lab Integrative Process¹ in which your Living Lab uses participatory methods and tools. That does not mean the Living Lab is not involved in the phases which are not selected in this question, e.g. your Living Lab could be active in exploiting solutions without using participatory tools and methods.

- Practice selection (e.g., idea selection, visioning/missioning exercises)
- Integration of stakeholders (e.g., community and network building, stakeholder mapping)
- Identification of barriers (e.g., analytical/research services, focus groups)
- Co-creation/co-design of solutions
- Piloting a solution (e.g., rapid prototyping, experimentation, usability, real-life testing)
- Evaluating a solution (e.g., end-user engagement, analytical/research services)
- Demonstrating a solution (e.g., equipment and facility rental, Living Lab as research/technology infrastructure)
- Exploiting a solution (e.g., deployment services, scaling up to other Living Labs)
- Our Living Lab is not using participatory tools & methods

What types of participatory tools and methods are used by your Living Lab (e.g., focus groups, interviews, brainstorming...)?

Non mandatory open question

How many times/year does your Living Lab externally share information, knowledge and results with its users/participants and external stakeholders? *

Information and knowledge can be shared via newsletters, updates on the website, events, social media, meetings...

- <1x/year
- 1x/year
- 2x/year
- 3x/year
- 4x/year
- 6x/year
- monthly
- more than monthly
- +

¹ <https://energylivinglab.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/Living-Lab-Integrative-Process-2022.pdf>

Impact and Value

This section assesses the level of participation in the development of *co-created values* (e.g., knowledge sharing, capacity building, network building) and even more importantly who they have been designed for. Furthermore, it investigates how the Living Lab is tracking impacts generated by the Living Lab. Two criteria are used to assess this part:

Co-created values, including

- user and stakeholder satisfaction (e.g., *influence on the process, capacity building*)
- degree of knowledge exchange among Living Lab stakeholders (e.g. community platform, knowledge hub)
- academic validation for researchers (e.g., *publications*)
- capacity building for/by network actors (e.g., *learning materials, trainings*)
- enabling innovative solutions

Impact of the Living Lab, including

- monitoring of impacts
- societal impact (e.g., *behavioral change, inclusion, diversity, digital gap*)
- economic impact (e.g., *patents, market disruption, speed of market penetration, decrease of cost*)
- environmental impact (e.g., *reduction of pollution, increase of air quality*)
- regulatory impact (e.g., *public policies, regulations*)
- technological impact (e.g., *increase TRL levels of technologies*)

Which types of learning materials (capacity building) has your Living Lab produced for different types of stakeholders over the last 3 years? *

Learning materials are any collection of materials to help achieve desired learning objectives.

Multiple choice*

Academic papers

Apps

Best practices

Datasets

E-courses

Infographics

Mentoring programs

Methods and tools

Non-scientific publications (e.g. handbooks, guidelines)

Podcasts

Policy briefs

Project sheets/leaflets

Trainings

Videos

Webinars

Websites

WIKI's

Other, namely:

None of the above

Does your Living Lab have methods in place to monitor the satisfaction of users and/or stakeholders concerning their involvement/influence on the innovation cycle and concerning knowledge sharing and capacity building? *

	yes	no
Frequency of involvement as user/stakeholder		
Degree of influence on the innovation cycle as user/stakeholder		
Knowledge sharing by the Living Lab		
Capacity building by the Living Lab		

Does your Living Lab uses standardized methods and forms to monitor the satisfaction of users and/or stakeholders across different Living Lab projects and activities? *

With standardized methods and forms we mean if you always ask the same satisfaction questions to your users/stakeholders.

Yes/no

How frequently are the following different types of impact of the Living Lab monitored by internal self-monitoring impact assessment processes beyond the scope of an individual Living Lab project? *

Measuring the frequency of impact assessments is an indicator of the strength of the Living Lab since it allows the Living Lab to change/strengthen its strategies and approaches based on these impact assessments.

	Not being monitored	<1x/ year	1x/ year	2X/ year	3x/ year	quarterly	bi-monthly	monthly
Societal impact								
Environmental impact								
Economic impact								
Regulatory impact								
Academic impact								
Technological impact								
Other, namely:								

What other type of impact is being monitored by your Living Lab?

Only if other in previous question ≠ not being monitored

NON mandatory open ended.

Stability and harmonization

The final section focuses on the (financial) *stability* of the Living Lab from a **macro-level** perspective, considering different aspects like the strength of the partnerships in the Living Lab and the revenue streams of the Living Lab. Next to this, it investigates replication (scale-up) of services, tools, methods and/or infrastructures of the Living Lab.

Finally, it looks at the level of harmonization of these strategic and operational building blocks beyond the Living Lab since harmonization will increase the sustainability of the Living Lab.

Stability, including

- level of financial sustainability based on a balanced and diversified set of fundings and revenue streams
- strength of partnerships
- degree of network collaboration

Harmonization and scale-up, including

- standardization of Living Lab procedures, processes, tools, methods and technologies
- replication of Living Lab processes, tools, methods, infrastructures and solutions
- cross-sectoral and geographical collaboration

How many partners have joined or left the managing group/governance team of your Living Lab over the last 3 years? *

Assessing if a Living Lab has a growing number of partners contributing to the Living Lab is an indicator for the stability of the Living Lab, assessing the departure of partners is an indicator for the strength of the partnerships within the Living Lab governance.

[Joined](#)

[Left](#)

Next to funding from funded projects a Living Lab can gather revenues from 'customers'.

Customers of the Living lab are organizations, governments who are directly paying the Living Lab to deliver services (e.g. testing and validation, co-creation, capacity building, advisory services, renting infrastructure of the LL). In other words, paying the Living Lab outside the scope of funded projects.

Some examples to explain:

- The council of the local city/municipality asks the Living Lab to engage the different stakeholders in co-creation activities and pays for the organization and/or facilitation of it.
- A group of farmers addresses the Living Lab to formulate some advice on how to organize their group of farmers concerning sustainable soil management practices.
- A private company could pay the Living Lab to use the infrastructure of the Living Lab to test their technical solution
- Even the EU of JRC (Joint Research Centre) could be a customer, paying the Living Lab directly to collaborate with them outside the scope of a funded project

Looking back at the last 3 years, how many different customers are/were paying for services or activities offered by your Living Lab?*

Open-ended

Looking at the overall finances of your Living Lab, approximately what % of revenues are provided by different funding streams? *

Please add % to reach 100% in total. We don't expect calculations to the 1% accuracy, an indication of 100-50-25-10-5% is more than sufficient.

A stable Living Lab is not depending on one type of financial resource. Therefore, with this question we want to assess the balance and diversification of the funding streams of the Living Lab.

- Public funding
- Project funding
- Private funding
- Revenues from own LL services
- Other revenues

What kind of other revenues are provided to your living lab? *

If other revenues in previous question

For how long are these different revenue streams secured? *

Multiple choice

Please mention the duration of all funding streams.

For instance, if Living Lab is involved in multiple projects, indicate the duration of all the projects (e.g. 1 can be funded for 1 to 2 years, while another is funded for 4 to 5 years). The same logic can be used concerning private and/or public funding streams.

Concerning the revenues from own LL services we want you to choose the answer since when your Living Lab is getting revenues from services/activities.

	Less than 1 year	1 to 2 years	2 to 3 years	3 to 4 years	4 to 5 years	+ 5 years
Public funding						
Project funding						
Private funding						
Revenues from own LL services						
Other, namely:						

How many Living Lab services, tools, methods and/or Living Lab infrastructures has your Living Lab developed over the last 3 years? *

Open ended, numeric fields

Living Lab services (e.g., testing and validation services, co-creation services, Living Lab project planning and management...)

Living Lab tools (e.g., stakeholder mapping, co-creation...)

Living Lab methods (e.g., user engagement process, testing procedures...)

Living Lab equipment and infrastructures (e.g., testing facilities, interaction platforms...)

Other, namely:

How many Living Lab services, tools, methods and/or Living Lab infrastructures developed by your organization/Living Lab have been replicated by partners of the managing group/governance team of your Living Lab over the last 3 years? *

Open ended numeric fields

Living Lab services (e.g., testing and validation services, co-creation services, Living Lab project planning and management...)

Living Lab tools (e.g., stakeholder mapping, co-creation...)

Living Lab methods (e.g., user engagement process, testing procedures...)

Living Lab equipment and infrastructures (e.g., testing facilities, interaction platforms...)

Other, namely:

None of the above

How many of Living Lab services, tools, methods and/or Living Lab infrastructures developed by your Living Lab have been replicated by other Living Lab (networks) over the last 3 years? *

Open ended, numeric fields

Living Lab services (e.g., testing and validation services, co-creation services, Living Lab project planning and management...)

Living Lab tools (e.g., stakeholder mapping, co-creation...)

Living Lab methods (e.g., user engagement process, testing procedures...)

Living Lab equipment and infrastructures (e.g., testing facilities, interaction platforms...)

Other, namely:

None of the above

Over the last 3 years, has your Living Lab been involved in projects and/or initiatives in which multiple Living Labs, cross-border/cross-sector, collaborate, using harmonized Living Lab processes, tools, methods and/or infrastructures? *

In these projects/initiatives, Living Labs use the same procedures, tools, methods, or infrastructures to run the project/initiative. For instance, they all communicate and interact with their end-users in the same way or they all test solutions with the same testing procedures.

Yes, a project/initiative using harmonized Living Lab processes (e.g. Living Lab integrative process)

Yes, a project using harmonized Living Lab services (e.g., testing and validation services, innovation network orchestration)

Yes, a project/initiative using harmonized Living Lab tools and/or methods (e.g. harmonized stakeholder mapping, experimentation tools)

Yes, a project/initiative using harmonized Living Lab equipment and infrastructure (e.g., testing facilities, interaction platforms)

None of the above

Feel free to elaborate on these harmonized projects and initiatives below

Would you like to add other comments and/or remarks concerning this self-assessment, feel free to add them here below.

END OF SURVEY